

Design Process for a Dual Pattern Reconfigurable Antenna based on flip-chip Aluminum Gallium Arsenide (AlGaAs) PIN diodes

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Abstract — A dual-pattern reconfigurable antenna comprising a torus-shaped metasurface controlled by flip-chip Aluminum Gallium Arsenide (AlGaAs) PIN diodes and a bicone antenna feed is investigated. A broadband bicone antenna operating between 14 and 34 GHz is initially optimized to enhance its realized gain and achieve 4.1 dBi at 29 GHz and 4.4 dBi at 30 GHz. The designed bicone is subsequently used as a feed for the torus-shaped metasurface. A torus-shaped metasurface capable of switching between reflection and transmission is investigated in two stages. Its geometry is optimized as a metallic reflector to reduce computational time. The dimensions of the reflector are optimized to improve the gains and lower the side lobe levels (SLL). The simulation of the reflector confirms that the torus reflector with the bicone feed achieves a realized gain of 16.3 dBi at 29 GHz and 17 dBi at 30 GHz. The proposed metasurface achieves transmission and reflection switching between 27.5 and 30.5 GHz by controlling the PIN diode state. Based on the results, the proposed system can operate in two distinct modes: omnidirectional and directional. The expected omnidirectional performance of the final system corresponds to that of the standalone bicone antenna, reduced by the metasurface insertion loss. In the directional mode, the realized gain and radiation pattern are determined by the combined response of the bicone antenna and torus-shaped metasurface reflector.

Keywords — Bicone, CST Microwave Studio, metasurface, PIN diodes, reconfigurable intelligent surface, torus reflector.

I. INTRODUCTION

A metasurface is a periodic or quasi-periodic structure engineered to exhibit properties rarely observed in naturally existing materials. Metasurfaces with and without active elements are used for several applications. Metasurfaces with active elements, such as PIN or varactor diodes, are mainly used for 5G communications and satellite uplink applications, such as earth-to-space communication [1]. Metasurfaces without any active elements can be integrated into antenna designs to enhance antenna parameters, such as reducing side lobe levels (SLL), improving gain, isolation improvement

between array elements in an antenna array, improving the operational bandwidth, and improving antenna efficiency [2, 3]. However, all these improvements are passive, meaning that once they are embedded into the antenna design, no further changes can be achieved. Advances in active element switching speed have enabled PIN diodes, such as the MACOM MADP series, to achieve switching times as fast as 2 to 3 ns.

Metasurfaces embedded with PIN diodes enable reconfigurability under a DC voltage bias and they are popularly used for various applications such as polarization conversion, frequency agility, and pattern reconfigurability [4-6]. Polarization conversion involves changing an antenna's linear polarization to vertical or changing right-hand circular polarization to left-hand circular polarization and vice versa [7, 8]. Frequency agility refers to the ability of an antenna to dynamically change its operating frequency without changing its dimensions [9]. Pattern reconfigurability involves converting an omnidirectional radiation pattern into a directional radiation pattern [10]. Pattern reconfigurability is useful for Internet of Things (IoT), 5G/6G, and satellite applications. At frequencies of 28 to 30 GHz, omnidirectional antennas with gains of 3 to 4 dBi provide limited coverage, and high-gain directive antennas with gains of 16 to 20 dBi are essential for providing coverage over longer distances. The 28 to 30 GHz frequency, which falls under the Ka-band (26.5 to 40 GHz), is used for satellite applications. According to Ofcom, the 29 to 30 GHz band is used for fixed terrestrial services, satellite earth-to-space uplinks, and fixed satellite services [11].

Researchers have presented several metasurface designs to achieve pattern reconfigurability. In [12], omnidirectional radiation patterns of a dipole operating at 3.3 to 4.2 GHz are converted to an endfire directive radiation pattern by activating PIN diodes. The dipole is supported by a reflector operated by a PIN diode. When the PIN diode is in the ON state, a closed circuit allows the reflector to change the dipole radiation pattern. Similarly, by integrating a metasurface into

a printed dipole operating at 26 to 28.5 GHz, beam steering over $\pm 30^\circ$ is achieved by changing the PIN diode state [13]. For this design, a metasurface for a printed dipole and, in total 6 PIN diodes are used. Along with beam steering, the metasurface also enhances the gain of the dipole, providing a 6 dBi total gain. A similar study concerns a printed dipole operating at 24 to 27.5 GHz that is used for 5G mobile terminals [14]. The planar dipole array consists of 4 dipole elements. Each dipole has two reconfigurable directors, each controlled by 3 diodes, i.e. 6 diodes for each dipole element. With 24 PIN diodes, an array of dipoles achieves pattern reconfigurability by providing two broadside patterns and one end-fire radiation pattern based on the diode operating state.

From the state-of-the-art, it is evident that metasurfaces with PIN diodes enable many possibilities. In this study, we propose the design of a metasurface unit cell with 3 Aluminum Gallium Arsenide (AlGaAs) PIN diodes. The proposed metasurface is designed and simulated using Computer Simulation Technology Microwave Studio (CST-MWS). The proposed metasurface with PIN diodes is an important component for designing a dual-pattern reconfigurable antenna. The design process for a dual-pattern reconfigurable antenna involves a reflector design, feed for the reflector, and a metasurface capable of switching between the transmission and reflection states. To determine the optimal dimensions for a torus reflector with a bicone, simulations are conducted for a torus reflector made of perfect electric conductor (PEC) material instead of meta-surface. This helps to reduce the simulation time and computational burden. In Section II, the design of the feed and reflector are discussed. Under Section II, the use of Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to optimize the realized gain of the bicone and a parametric study of the reflector geometry to lower the SLL and enhance realized gain are discussed in detail. In Section III, the design of the metasurface and the design process involved in obtaining a dual-pattern reconfigurable antenna are discussed.

Fig. 1. Bicone antenna (a) front view (b) S11.

II. DESIGN OF THE FEED AND REFLECTOR OF THE TORUS REFLECTOR ANTENNA

A bicone antenna is selected as the feed because of its omnidirectional radiation patterns and relatively better bandwidth than a dipole, monopole, and bowtie [15]. Similarly, a torus reflector, which is doughnut-shaped, helps to focus the signals by placing the bicone at the torus opening. In terms of geometry, a quarter of a torus is an elliptical cylinder bent twice along the lateral (x-axis) and longitudinal (y-axis) axes [16].

Fig. 2. E-field radiation patterns of a bicone antenna at: (a) 29 GHz, (b) 30 GHz.

A. Design of the feed (bicone antenna)

In Fig. 1(a) the proposed bicone antenna along with the key parameters used for optimizing the realized gain are shown. To tune a bicone, the key parameters are the bicone length, the maximum cone radius, and the minimum cone radius. By optimizing these parameters, the realized gain is improved at 29 and 30 GHz. To optimize these three parameters, PSO is used in CST-MWS. The optimization process focuses on improving the bicone's realized gain without degrading its bandwidth. This is shown in Fig. 1(b) where the S11 of the optimized bicone is compared with that of the base model. From these results, it is observed that the optimized bicone operates over a broad frequency band of 14 to 34 GHz. In terms of radiation patterns and realized gains, the radiation

Fig. 3. Proposed torus reflector antenna (a) front view (b) dimensions.

Fig. 4. Radiation patterns of the torus reflector antenna in (a) E-plane at 29 GHz (b) E-plane at 30 GHz (c) H-plane at 29 GHz and, (d) H-plane at 30 GHz.

patterns of the bicone for the optimized case is compared with those of the base model at 29 and 30 GHz, as shown in Fig. 2. From Fig. 2(a) and 2(b) it is observed that by optimizing the bicone length, maximum cone radius and minimum cone radius the realized gain is improved by 0.9 and 0.7 dB at 29 and 30 GHz, respectively.

B. Design of the reflector (torus reflector)

In Fig. 3(a) the proposed torus reflector along with the bicone feed antenna is shown. In Fig. 3(b) the dimensions of the reflector are depicted. The reflector antenna has a diameter of 244 mm, with a bicone antenna positioned at the reflector opening. When designing the torus reflector the key tunable parameters are the bent angles along the longitudinal axis (y-

TABLE I.
DIMENSIONS OF THE PROPOSED TORUS REFLECTOR

Name	W (mm)	L (mm)	a (mm)	b (mm)	bent angle along x/y-axis
Dimensions	270	244	43	47.5	180°/60°

axis), bent angles along the lateral axis (x-axis), gain of the bicone, and extra metallic arms on the top and bottom regions of the reflector. While the bent angles along both the y- and x-axes impact the shape of the radiation pattern, the gain of the bicone antenna helps to improve the overall reflector gain; extra metallic arms on the top and bottom of the reflector are used to tune the SLL in the E-plane. In our parametric study, we will be discussing the impact of extra metallic arms, removal of complete metallic arms (i.e. $a=b=0$ mm) and the metallic region extended laterally (along the x-axis, $b=270$ mm). The use of extra metallic arms is referred to as the proposed case, the removal of complete metallic arms is referred to as case 1, The laterally extended metallic arm region (along the x-axis) is referred to as case 2.

Final optimized dimensions of the proposed reflector antenna are presented in Table I. The radiation patterns of the torus reflector antenna are shown in Fig. 4. The radiation patterns at 29 and 30 GHz in both the E-plane and H-plane for the proposed case are compared with those of case 1 and case 2. From the radiation patterns presented in Fig. 4(a) and Fig. 4(b), it can be observed that a pencil beam with a HPBW of 3° and SLL of -14 dB is obtained in the E-plane. For the H-plane, a fan beam with an HPBW of 102° and an SLL of -4.4 dB, which requires improvements, is obtained.

TABLE II.
REALIZED GAIN AND SLL

Name	Realized gain at boresight (dBi)	SLL (dB)
Proposed (E/H-plane) at 29 GHz	16.3/16.3	-14/ -4.4
Case 1 (E/H-plane) at 29 GHz	16.3/ 16.3	-15/ -4
Case 2 (E/H-plane) at 29 GHz	15.9/ 15.2	-9.3/ -1
Proposed (E/H-plane) at 30 GHz	17/ 17.1	-12/ -4
Case 1 (E/H-plane) at 30 GHz	15.9/ 15.9	-12/ -2
Case 2 (E/H-plane) at 30 GHz	13.5/ 13.5	-6/ 0

In Table II, the realized gain of the reflector antenna in the E- and H-plane for all three cases at 29 and 30 GHz are presented. For the proposed case, at 29 GHz, a realized gain of 16.3 dBi with an SLL of -14 dB and a realized gain of 17 dBi with an SLL of -12 dB at 30 GHz are achieved. Similarly, in the E-plane, realized gains of 16.3 dBi and 17.1 dBi are obtained at 29 and 30 GHz, respectively. From the radiation patterns shown in Fig. 4 and from the gain and SLL discussed in Table II, it can be observed that removing the excess metallic part at the top and bottom regions of the torus helps to improve the SLL and realized gain. Compared with case 1, for the proposed case, maintaining extra metallic arms doesn't show a significant improvement in the realized gain and SLL at 29 GHz. However, at 30 GHz, maintaining these extra metallic arms for the proposed case allows for an

improvement of 1 dB in the realized gain and an improvement of 2 dB in the SLL. These extra metallic arms allows to focus the beam at the feed location thus lowering the SLL, thereby improving the realized gain.

Fig. 5. Design of the proposed metasurface (a) top view and, (b) bottom view.

III. METASURFACE WITH PIN DIODES

A. Metasurface Design

A metasurface with three layers, with PEC on the top and bottom layers and a substrate in the middle layer, is designed. Active components, such as PIN diodes, are used to provide switchable functionalities. The proposed metasurface uses three PIN diodes. When all three PIN diodes are 'ON' a transmission state is realized, and when the two diodes on the top layer are 'ON' while the diode in the bottom layer is 'OFF', a reflection state is achieved. In Fig. 5(a) and Fig. 5(b) top view and a bottom view of the proposed metasurface are presented. The proposed metasurface has dimensions of 5.37 mm \times 4.3 mm \times 0.83 mm with a substrate of thickness 0.78 mm. The substrate is made of TLY-5 with a dielectric constant of 2.2 and a loss tangent of 0.0009 at 10 GHz. The optimized dimensions for the proposed metasurface are $x = 5.37$ mm, $y = 4.37$ mm, $a1 = 1.17$ mm, $b1 = 0.38$ mm, $w1 = w2 = 3.19$ mm, $l1 = 1.13$ mm, $a2 = 2.15$ mm, $b2 = 0.3$ mm, $w3 = 1.92$ mm, $l3 = 1.4$ mm, $a3 = 1.35$ mm and $b3 = 0.51$ mm. The unit cell is modelled and simulated in CST-MWS.

During the simulations, a Touchstone file of MADP-000907 from MACOM is used. This is a heterojunction PIN diode designed for RF and millimeter-wave applications, typically implemented with a flip-chip packaging technique. A PIN diode consists of three layers: an anode, which is an acceptor-doped p-type, an undoped intrinsic layer, and a cathode, which is a donor-doped n-type layer. In a heterojunction PIN diode, different semiconductor materials are used for the p-type, intrinsic, and n-type layers to obtain low capacitance and low series resistance at millimeter-wave frequencies. To achieve high electron mobility, which is obtained by lowering the series resistance and capacitance, aluminum is used for the p-type layer, and gallium arsenide is used for the intrinsic and n-type layers [17].

During simulations, when the PIN diodes are assigned in CST-MWS, to improve the simulation accuracy, a vacuum sheet with dimensions equivalent to a PIN diode is modelled between the PEC rings of the metasurface, and a face port is assigned. When compared with the lumped element assignment, where two points are selected between the PEC rings to assign a lumped port, using a vacuum sheet to assign a discrete face port provides a uniform distribution of the electric field around the PEC of the metasurface. This improves the simulation accuracy to extract the transmission

and reflection coefficient. Simulations are performed in the frequency domain solver of CST-MWS, which is based on the finite element method (FEM). A total of 60,431 tetrahedrons are generated with dense meshing around the metallic regions, discrete face port and coarse meshing for the substrate. Simulations are performed using an i9-13900KF processor @ 3 GHz (32-cores) and 128 GB of RAM. It takes around 57 s to complete the simulation [18].

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Simulation results for the (a) transmission coefficient and, (b) reflection coefficient of the metasurface.

To understand the influence of the slots and substrate dimensions of the metasurface on the transmission and reflection coefficients, a parametric study is presented in Fig. 6. In Fig.6(a) the transmission coefficient of the metasurface for the proposed case is compared with those of the other two cases. Similarly in Fig. 6(b) the reflection coefficient of the metasurface for the proposed case is compared with those of the other two cases. The two cases compared are, case 1 when all the slots in the top and bottom layers, i.e. $a_1=b_1=a_2=b_2=a_3=b_3=0$ mm, and case 2, when the dimensions of the substrate are reduced to $x=4.47$ mm (proposed case $x=5.37$ mm) and $y=3.57$ mm (proposed case $y=4.3$ mm). It should be noted that for case 2, only the substrate dimensions are changed, and all other parameter dimensions are same as the proposed case dimensions. For the proposed case, a transmission coefficient better than 0.9 (magnitude) over the frequency range 27 to 37 GHz and reflection coefficient better than 0.9 (magnitude) over the frequency range 27.5 to 30.5 GHz is achieved. From these comparisons, it can be observed that the dimensions of the

substrate play an important role, and by changing these dimensions, there is a resonance shift. Although the slot dimensions have negligible impact on the transmission coefficient, they are essential for controlling the reflection coefficient.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. Working principle of dual-pattern reconfigurable antenna (a) omnidirectional pattern (b) directional pattern.

Finally, once all the geometric parameters such as W , L , a , b of the reflector part in a torus reflector with a bicone are optimized, replacing the metallic region of the reflector with the proposed metasurface controlled by PIN diodes converts the conventional reflector [19] into a reconfigurable intelligent surface [20]. The working principle of the proposed dual-pattern reconfigurable antenna is shown in Fig. 7. In Fig. 7(a) and Fig. 7(b), the optimized torus reflector PEC part is replaced by the proposed metasurface. When the metasurface operates in the transmission mode, the electromagnetic waves from the bicone antenna pass through the metasurface, resulting in an omnidirectional radiation pattern, as shown in Fig. 7(b). Conversely, when the metasurface operates in the reflection mode, the electromagnetic waves are reflected back toward the bicone, producing a directional radiation pattern, as shown in Fig. 7(b). In transmission mode, the antenna achieves an omnidirectional radiation pattern with realized gains of 3.65 dBi at 29 GHz and 3.95 dBi at 30 GHz,

accounting for an insertion loss of 0.45 dB from the metasurface at both frequencies. In the reflection mode, the antenna provides a directional radiation pattern with realized gains of 16.04 dBi at 29 GHz and 16.55 dBi at 30 GHz, considering insertion losses of 0.26 dB and 0.45 dB, respectively. The insertion losses originate from the metasurfaces incorporating the PIN diodes. When a PEC region of the reflector is replaced by these metasurfaces, it is essential to account for the additional insertion loss introduced by the metasurfaces.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we discussed the design and analysis of a reconfigurable metasurface, a broadband bicone antenna, and the optimization of torus reflector geometry. The proposed metasurface, operating over the 27.5 to 30.5 GHz band, serves as a key component for reconfigurable intelligent surface. To achieve reconfigurability, the metallic portion of the torus reflector is replaced with the proposed metasurface, controlled by AlGaAs PIN diodes. The insertion losses introduced by the metasurface are included in the gain calculations. The metasurface exhibits relatively low losses of 0.45 dB at both 29 and 30 GHz in the transmission state, and 0.26 dB at 29 GHz and 0.45 dB at 30 GHz in the reflection state. These low-loss characteristics prove the suitability of the proposed metasurface for practical dual-pattern reconfigurable antenna systems. By optimizing the reflector geometry, a broadband bicone antenna with a realized gain of 3.65 dBi at 29 GHz is transformed into a highly directive beam with a realized gain of 16.04 dBi. Similarly, at 30 GHz, the bicone's 3.95 dBi realized gain is enhanced to 16.55 dBi after considering the metasurface insertion loss.

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